

1 **Irf silencing by papillomavirus E2.**

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6 HPV E2 is the viral transcriptional activator but likely has a multitude of functions separate from the
7 E1-associated viral trans-activation event that remain undefined. We demonstrate here by ectopic
8 expression of HPV E2 in human cells and measurement of total transcription following next generation
9 RNA-sequencing silencing of *Irf7* and *Irf9* by human papillomavirus E2 protein.

10 Citations

11 1. Honda, K., Yanai, H., Negishi, H., Asagiri, M., Sato, M., Mizutani, T., Shimada, N., Ohba, Y.,
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13 interferon-dependent immune responses. *Nature*, 434(7034), pp.772-777.

14 GSE121627